

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AGBENYAH****FIRST NAME: JOEL****PROGRAM CODE: DEPI****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 11%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2019 on Windows 10

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What is the purpose of response papers at EUCLID University?
 - To copy and paste material
 - To avoid interaction with course material
 - To skip assignments
 - To demonstrate progress and critical reflection¹**

2. What is the recommended approach to handling limitations in a dissertation?
 - To acknowledge them and discuss their implications for future research²**
 - To ignore them

¹ EUCLID, *Initial Student Orientation* (Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2024), 5.

² James P Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 59.

- To repeat the research questions
 - To confuse the readers
3. In Turabian style, what is the correct order for elements in a footnote citation for a book?
- Title, author, publication date
 - Author, title, publication date**³
 - Publication date, author, title
 - Author, publication date, title
4. Which of the following is NOT a recommended guideline for tables and figures according to the WHO Style Guide?
- Include a title above each table or figure
 - Provide a source for each table or figure
 - Place tables and figures within the text**⁴
 - Number tables and figures sequentially
5. How should research questions relate to the problem statement in a dissertation?
- They should be unrelated
 - They should be contradictory

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers.*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., Ninth edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 149.

⁴ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide*, Second Edition (Geneva: World Health Organization Press, 2013), 50.

- They should logically follow from the statement of the problem⁵**
- They should be completely different
6. How should the components of research questions be judged in a dissertation?
- In terms of length
- In terms of social significance and feasibility⁶**
- In terms of complexity
- In terms of repetition
7. According to the WHO Style Guide, how should acronyms be introduced for the first time in a document?
- Parentheses immediately after the acronym
- By giving the term in full, followed by the abbreviation in parentheses⁷**
- No parentheses are needed
- In square brackets after the acronym
8. How should multiple authors be listed in a bibliography entry in Turabian style?
- First author only
- Last name followed by first name for each author

⁵ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 29.

⁶ Ibid.

⁷ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide*, 19.

- Last name followed by initials for each author⁸**
- Full names of all authors

9. What is the purpose of including additional findings in a dissertation?

- To confuse the readers
- To extend the length of the dissertation
- To provide further investigation beyond the original research questions⁹**
- To repeat the research questions

10. How are subsequent citations of the same source formatted in footnotes according to the Turabian style?

- Ibid¹⁰**
- Author's last name only
- Full citation repeated
- Shortened citation

⁸ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers.*, 230.

⁹ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 55.

¹⁰ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 166.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.